

The use of humic acids and their salts to extract gallium from the fly ash of brown coal thermal power plants

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The use of humic acids and their salts is of considerable interest for the development of environmentally sound technologies for the extraction of valuable metals from man-made waste. The use of natural and low-toxic reagents, which are humic substances, in the processing of fly ash from brown coal thermal power plants containing high concentrations of dispersed elements such as gallium, is a particularly promising area that minimizes the use of aggressive chemicals [1].

We used the fly ash from Novosibirsk CHPP-3 as a research object. This ash is characterized by a significant gallium content, up to 220 g/t. The main attention was paid to the study of the effectiveness of humic acids and their sodium salt (sodium humate) as complexing agents in the mechanochemical activation of ash in comparison with traditional reagents (EDTA, EDF, carbamide). The mechanochemical treatment was carried out on a planetary mill, which contributed to the destruction of the silicate matrix of the ash and increased the availability of the target elements [2].

The highest efficiency of converting gallium to a water-soluble form (81% of the total content) was achieved when the ash was mechanochemically activated using sodium humate. The ICP-MS data confirms this result. At the same time, the use of aggressive acids for the decomposition of the sample was not required. Unlike sodium humate, treatment with humic acids did not show a significant effect. Only one percent of gallium was extracted using this treatment method. This highlights the importance of the reagent shape. The results obtained demonstrate the prospects of using humic acid salts to create effective and environmentally friendly methods for extracting gallium from waste from brown coal thermal power plants.

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References

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